

An Investigation into Herbal Remedies for Asthma in Mach Tehsil, Kachhi (Bolan) District, Balochistan

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Abstract

People of all ages can develop asthma, a persistent lung condition. Asthma is the respiratory disease recognized by coughing and shortness of breath it is caused when our lungs or airways of lungs get damaged. The study aims to collect data from local people of Mach, Bolan, Balochistan for the treatment of Asthma with medicinal Plants. Primary methods used to gather data from 115 residents of Tehsil Mach Bolan. The results were analyzed using a variety of ethnobotanical indices, including Use Report (UR), Frequency Citation (FC), Use Value (UV), Relative Frequency Citation (RFC), and Family Importance Value (FIV). A total of 30 plant species belonging to 30 families were identified for their potential medical applications. With three species, the Fabaceae family was projected to be the most prevalent in Tehsil Mach Bolan. The leaves, seeds, and roots of each plant are used most often

as infusions, with a little amount being used as a powder or capsule decoction. *Papaver somniferum* (Kokinar) was shown to have the highest RFC value (0.08). The *Boswellia serrata* (Gound Katra) has the highest usage value recorded (1.3). Green tea, or *Camellia sinensis*, had the highest use report (10). *Papaver somniferum* (Kokinar) has the highest FC value (10). There are several medicinal plants in Balochistan, and the locals still use them for therapeutic

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purposes in their daily life. The study makes it feasible to look at studies on medicinal plant that are used to treat the symptoms of asthma in older adults and smokers. While it may take a while for herbal supplements to treat asthma, The ailment may be cured from its leaves with regular use. For the first time in the district, the ethnobotanical results offer quantitative data on the diversity of therapeutic plants. For further drugs, the phytochemical composition and toxicity of the most often utilised plants should be examined.

Introduction

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory disease of the airways characterised by frequent bouts of airway obstruction and wheezing. The presence of eosinophilic infiltration in the airways has been recognised since 1908, when it was first reported in a patient who died of asthma (Ellis AG 1908). However, inflammation was not considered the cause of asthma until recently.

Over the past 15 years, almost all of the research on inflammation as a cause of asthma has focused on this subject. The invention of flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy in the early 1980s made it possible to assess the airways of asthmatic patients with distinct lung function when the illness was not active. These investigations showed that even in asymptomatic patients, airway inflammation existed. Seminal articles describing CD4 were published around the same time. Kim J. et al. (1985) and TR et al. (1986) disclosed the subgroups and their functional impacts and further research revealed that the cells were found in asthmatic patients' airways (D S et al., 1992). The idea that the cells encourage asthma was sparked by these findings as well as the link between cytokines and allergic disorders. Research on inflammation as a cause of asthma has been nearly solely concentrated on this topic over the past 15 years.

Mononuclear cells, mainly eosinophils and CD4 T lymphocytes, penetrate the airway wall in asthma. Compared to controls, asthmatics' airways include different numbers of mast cells, neutrophils, plasma cells, and macrophages. According to study using electron microscopy, degranulation is an indication of active mast cells (Laitinen et al, 1997).

Deadly asthma affects all airways save the biggest, and small airways (24 mm) are often destroyed and all airways—aside from the largest are impacted in deadly asthma. The airway epithelium metaplasia into cells that secrete mucus and the mucous glands enlarge. The mucous glands grow and the airway epithelium metaplasia into mucus- secreting cells. The subepithelial layer, which is 4–5 microns thick in healthy individuals, can be 7–23 microns thick in asthmatics due to the direct deposition of collagen (Types I, III, and V), fibronectin, and tenascin in the lamina reticularis beneath the foundation membrane (Roberts et al, 1997; Roche et al, 1989). Inflammation and airway remodeling lead to airway obstruction, which causes wheezing and dyspnea, and airway hyper responsiveness (AHR). AHR, sometimes known as "twitchy" airways, is characterized by an elevated bronchoconstriction response to an ambiguous stimulus (Boushey, 1982). By inhaling nonselective stimuli that cause bronchoconstriction in all asthmatics, such as meth choline, the reaction can be assessed in a lab setting. This is usually done using dose-response curves.

Medicinal plants have been used for thousands of years to prevent, diagnose, treat, or cure a variety of diseases and conditions, offering a holistic and all- natural approach to healthcare. The world still mostly uses ethno medicine to cure common illnesses, even with the expansion of the pharmaceutical sector (Khan et al., 2018). Components found in medicinal plants can help treat or prevent infections and illnesses in humans. People have been using plants to treat illnesses and lessen their symptoms since ancient times. Alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenes, and essential oils are the most significant compounds found in therapeutic plants. According to Okoli et al. (2007), Anti-inflammatory, immune-modulatory, antihistaminic, smooth muscle relaxant, and antiallergic properties are all necessary for asthma. Anti-inflammatory, immune- modulatory, antihistaminic, smooth muscle relaxant, and antiallergic properties are all necessary for asthma.

One of the main reasons for the increasing use of medicinal plants for Asthma and other diseases in traditional medicine is the general lack of access to modern medical facilities in these areas (Khan et al., 2015). According to ethno medical research conducted in northwest Pakistan region by Adnan et al. (2014), 107 species are utilized in primary healthcare to cure a variety of illnesses. Important data for medication development and discovery utilizing medicinal plants is provided by ethno medical surveys. As natural resources, plants are essential to human well-being. However, plant variety has been greatly impacted (Husain et al., 2008; (Ahmed et al., 2010; Mahmood et al., 2011;Shinwari, 2010).

. The quality of life is greatly reduced by asthma, which affects one's ability to work, engage in leisure physical activities, and maintain emotional stability. Achieving total clinical control, which entails efficiently managing symptoms and reducing potential dangers, is the main objective of asthma treatment. This entails symptom relief, lowering inhaler use, increasing physical activity, and improving lung function. Preventing asthma flare-ups, avoiding fast lung function decrease, and making sure that drugs don't have adverse effects are all essential to reducing future risks (Mehrotra and Mehrotra, 2005).

Asthma prevalence varies around the world, with industrialized nations—especially Australia, the

United Kingdom, and New Zealand—having higher rates. Between 7% and 18% of Nigerians suffer from asthma, with 14.1% of pupils in the southwest, 14.2% of adolescents in the southeast, and adults in the north-central areas having the condition. Age-related differences exist in the sex ratio for asthma (Erhabor Egbagbe EE 2010; ISAAC 1998; Masoli M et al 2004; Ibe Ele 2004).

Making breathing difficult. There isn't a longterm cure, although medications and lifestyle changes can help control it. Although there isn't a permanent solution, medicines and lifestyle modifications can help manage it. An asthma management plan, medication, and lifestyle changes can all help reduce the symptoms of asthma.

Material and methods

Data were collected using semi-structured interviews, fast appraisal technique surveys, free listening, and personal observation. Quantitative indices such as Use Report (UR), Use Value (UV), Frequency Citation (FC), and Relative Frequency Citation (RFC) were calculated for each medicinal plant studied.

Study area

The examination was conducted in one location of District Bolan, Tehsil Mach.

District Much geo-ethnographical overview

Mach district is a subdistrict of Bolan tehsil, which is situated in Pakistan's Balochistan province. Tehsil Mach is located about 45 kilometres southeast of Quetta in the northeastern region of Balochistan. The native tongue, the Brahui language, is mostly utilised in speaking, and there are a lot of Brahui people in the district. Other ethnic groups use Urdu. Sumalani Balochi, Hazara, Hindus, and every ethnic group in the district speak Brahui to communicate with one another. A very tiny percentage of the tribal people, or 6.7% of all migrants, migrate to other countries each year during the winter months, travelling to Kachi (Bolan district) with their families and little livestock. October marks the beginning of migration, which lasts until November. In March, the migrants make their way back to Mach.

Socio-economic condition of the area

The socioeconomic state of the regionThe district of Mach has been endowed with a wide variety of flora, including many medicinal plants. Due to a lack of health facilities, the rural parts of the district continue to rely on medicinal plants for their medical needs. The primary source of income for the majority of the population in the area—nearly 50%— is agriculture. Wheat, barley, cumin, fodder, melon, potatoes, and other vegetables are important crops that are grown. Some locals gather medicinal plants from plains, mountains, deserts, and forests and sell them to traditional herb vendors in the area for extremely low costs. The pharmaceutical corporations then purchase these plants from local traditional herb vendors at competitive costs. The economical situation of mines will significantly improve if the sustainable use of wild plants and the production of therapeutic plants are

encouraged in the region. Coal is transported throughout the nation. Mach District Bolan is home to one of the biggest central jails.

PAKISTAN

BALOCHISTAN

KACHI BOLAN

Fig 1 Map of Pakistan Balochistan, and district Kachi Bolan

Field Interview

Free listing interviews with randomly chosen informants and field interviews with key informants chosen following free listing were used to gather ethnobotanical data. The questionnaire primarily focused on the traditional beliefs and ethnobotanical claims of local communities and surrounding individuals, and the interviews were conducted in the local languages of Brahui and Urdu because the first author of the ethnobotanical information is a local person in the area.

A total of 115 local residents were interviewed. Interviews were conducted with 76 women, 29 men, and 10 men who were traditional healers. Three age groups were created from the informants: 22–39, 40–55, and 22–39–40–55–60–80 years old. Every informal gathering took place in one of the district's five villages: Kolpur, Mach, Dhadar, or Abagum Gulp.

Identification, collection of deposition medicinal plants

Only during the summer months in the highlands, such as Koh-e-Marghat, were the plants gathered for the purpose of treating asthma in the district of Mach Refuge (2020–2024). Koh-e-Seinkoni The plants can be dehydrated and stored, according to Koh-e-Gando Jain and Rao (1977). Herbarium systems are used to confirm plant identification. Nasir and Ali (1970-1979), Ali and Nasir (1980-1989), Nasir and Ali (1989-1991), and Qaiser and Ali (1993-2007) have all been observed. Herbarium specimens were deposited to the botany department at SBK University. Only during the summer months in the highlands, such as Koh-e-Marghat, were the plants gathered for the purpose of treating asthma in the district of Mach Refuge (2020–2024). Koh-e-Seinkoni The plants can be dehydrated and stored, according to Koh-e-Gando Jain and Rao (1977). Herbarium systems are used to confirm plant identification. Nasir and Ali (1970-1979), Ali and Nasir (1980-1989), Nasir and Ali (1989-1991), and Qaiser and Ali (1993-2007) have all been observed. Herbarium specimens were deposited to the botany department at SBK University.

Quantitative analysis of ethnobotanical results

Analysis of ethnobotanical findings quantitatively using quantitative metrics and directories, quantitative data was gathered and examined.

Use value (UV)

Use value is a common metric for quantifying the prevalence of beneficial plants is utilization cost. This formula (Phillips et al., 1994) defines UV, where UV is the total of the species practice values for, say, a species of plant, and it specifies the entire form that the respondents filled out. The plants were subjected to intense UV treatment (as indicated more often). The hand-me-down paperwork for all species is called an application report (UR), and

it is used in the healing of ailment

$$UV = \sum U/N$$

Use report

Report on use for each species, the use report (UR) is checked. It examines how the species is used overall by all of its members. The number of residents is counted. They provide all of the species' use categories along with the total number of uses in each use category. (Prance and others, 1987)

Frequency citation (FC) and relative frequency citation (RFC)

Both relative frequency citation (RFC) and frequency citation (FC) are used to confirm the use of medicinal herbs. The relative frequency citation (RFC) index was calculated using the following formulas (Prado-de-Tardío Santayana, 2008): $F=C$ (number of times a specific variable was mentioned/total number of times that all variability was mentioned) $\times 100$.

$$RFC = FC/N (0 < RFC < 1)$$

The valuable species FC frequency, or frequency citation, is calculated by dividing the number of respondents (N) by the total number of participants in the survey. The RFC value varies from 0 (no plant is as valuable as regarded) to 1 (everyone declares it to be useful). The use type is not taken into consideration by the index RFC (a use report, or UR, is a single record for use for a plant that a person mentions).

Fidelity level (FL)

Level of fidelity (FL) The fidelity level (Friedman et al., 1986) formula for identifying additional plant species used to treat the same group is $FL = (N P/N \times 100)$. When N P is the number of residents mentioning the beneficial plants for a demanding illness, N is the number of residents citing the species for any illness. Its importance lies in the fact that, according to the study's informants, it is frequently utilized to treat specific sorts of illnesses.

Family importance value (FIV)

The significance of plant families is acknowledged by the FIV. It is a social importance catalogue that ethno botanists can use to determine a biological plant taxon's worth. We utilize the formula

$$FIV = FC (\text{family})/N \times 100 \text{ to estimate FIV.}$$

N is the overall number of participants in the study, but FC is the number of people who say "family". Families of unoccupied species are classified as residents based on their family importance value (FIV). According to Vitalini et al. (2013), it was estimated by calculating the proportion of informants who mentioned the family.

Results and Discussion

150 residents of the Mach district were interviewed, including traditional healers of various ages (50 per percent males, 40 per percent women, and 10 per cent men practitioners). Two age categories were created from the informants. Since asthma affects people of all ages, the majority of the informants were between the ages of 30 and 60, and they knew more about herbs that can treat the condition. Most of the interviewees who participated in the study use plants and plant-based products as part of traditional natural asthma treatments. A total of thirty species were mentioned in 4.1 along with their local names, family names, uses, and plants used for the medicinal value use report (UR), use value frequency citation (UV), frequency citation (FC), and relative frequency citation (RFC). In table 1, the most species-rich families were Fabaceae, Apiaceae, Poaceae, and Piperaceae, each with two species. The most typically utilized plant components were the leaves and roots; each plant was frequently employed in decoction and infusion, with a minor percentage also being used in capsules and powder extraction.

Ethnobotanical plants are essential for sustaining asthma symptoms. There are numerous plants that can be used to cure asthma, but this article only covered thirty.

Additionally, some plants, like *Thymus vulgaris* (Izbotak), can be used to treat multiple illnesses, such as coughing and chest pain. By efficiently reducing inflammation and blood levels of lipids like cholesterol and triglycerides, *Nigella sativa* (kalonji) lowers the risk of heart disease. *Trachyspermum* (Ajwain) also helps with respiratory issues. The seeds are well known for keeping the throat and lungs clear of pollutants. People with respiratory issues benefit from ajwain water's ability to relax the airway. Turmeric (Haladi) lowers high levels of androgen and antioxidant stress, as well as aid in raising insulin levels), *Papaver somniferum* (Kokinar) had the greatest RFC value (0.08), while *Camellia sinensis* (green tea) had the highest usage value (10). The black cardamom (Badielaichi) had the highest use reported (0.75) (Table) the most prevalent family in both dry woods and tropical rainforests in Africa and the United States is the Fabaceae (Burham and Johnson 2004). In addition to helping to preserve cultural traditions and biodiversity, traditional knowledge of medicinal plants, their usage by indigenous healers and current drug research benefit local residents' health and well-being. Emir (2011)

Herbal Drug Preparation Methods

Among herbal medicinal preparations, decoction (36% with 11 species), powder (16% with 5 species), and infusion (16% with 5 species) are extensively employed (Fig. 1). The outcomes of the extensive usage of infusion and decoction align with the research conducted by Ahmed et al. (2014) and Gurdal and Kultur (2013). According to reports, the most popular preparation technique was decoction, which was followed by infusion and powder. The study found seven internal application methods: roasting, toasting, oil/paste/tea, decoction, infusion, powder, grinding, heating, water, and flour. Since some species required a preparation method, the direct use of some species was also documented. Among the many plant parts utilized during the study, the leaves and roots were employed most frequently (16% of each) (Fig. 2). Additionally, it was observed that leaves are more readily available and subtly more abundant in nature than other plant parts, which may account for their use. In contrast, the region's frequent use of whole plants may be due to the region's mountainous terrain, which receives little rainfall, and the fact that most plants are herbaceous and wild bushes (Bonet et al., 1999; Neves et al., 2009). As a result, people gather plant pieces from the air and frequently utilize them for infusion and decoction addition to being prevalent in our study, the herbaceous habit is a ubiquitous and widespread ecological occurrence worldwide (Ibrar et al., 2007; Jan et al., 2011). In a similar vein, Ahmed et al. (2014) noted that the Chill Valley of Pakistan is primarily a herbaceous plant-eating region. Similar findings were found by Qureshi (2012) in the Hingol National Park region of Balochistan, where leaves (21.28%) are utilized more frequently than whole plants (27.13%) for the manufacture of treatments. Additionally, it is observed that when a single plant part—such as a leaf, flower, or fruit—is needed, the locals gather the entire plant rather than just the necessary portion. This practice of gathering plant parts has had a negative impact on the population number. Additionally, the indigenous people used a variety of plant parts, including roots (13%), leaves (30%), seeds (23%), flowers (6%) and other parts (fig. 2). These wild populations' capacity to survive has been further strained by their extreme reliance on leaves, roots, and seeds. The least used parts are the flowers.

Quantitative Analysis

Use value (UV), use report (UR) and relative frequency of Citation (RFC)

The relative frequency of citations (RFC), usage value (UV), and use report (UR) *Zingiber officinale* (0.57), *Juglans regia* (0.25), *Camellia sinensis* (0.8), *Ephedra sinica* (0.6), *Hordeum vulgare* (0.5), *Boswellia Serrata* (1.3), *Papaver somniferum* (1.1), *Trachyspermum ammi* (1), and *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (0.75) had the greatest usage values. Although

Boswellia serrata has the highest use value and the advantage of reducing asthma, according to a study by Leung et al. (1996), some of the families' medicinal plants and their bioactive extracts are essential for treating asthma. *Camellia sinensis* (10), *Papaver somniferum* (9), *Trigonella frenum-graecum* (8), and *Allium sativum* (6 each) had the most usage reports, whereas *Papaver somniferum* had the lowest use reports (Elsevier 2015).

Papaver somniferum (0.08), *Camellia sinensis*, Jaggery, Black pepper, Black cardamom, *Trigonella frenum-graecum* (0.05 each), and *Trachyspermum ammi* (0.03) had the highest RFC values, while *Nigella sativa* (0.01) and *Hordeumvulgare* (0.01) had the lowest (Table 1). In District Kachi Bolan, these species are the most commonly utilized plants and the most frequently used medicinal herbs, according to the majority of informants.

Thymus (1) had the lowest FC, whereas *Papaver somniferum* (10) and Jaggery and *Camellia sinensis* (8 both) had the highest FC. According to the study, these species are unique to the number of informants cited.

Indigenous Knowledge in the study area, Mach Bolan

Particularly in the rural areas of the district, the majority of the population lacks formal education, and their main sources of income are agriculture and livestock. *Trigonella frenum graecum*, *Papaver somniferum*, *Allium sativum*, *Ephedra sinica*, *Thymus*, *Num Harmala*, and *Boswellia serrata* are among the medicinal plants that some residents gather and sell to nearby herb vendors for modest prices. These vendors then resell the plants to pharmaceutical corporations at a premium. There are serious risks in the area due to overshadowing, suburbanisation, and the removal of medicinal plants. These hazards increase the likelihood of extinction and demand that the government exercise cautious supervision over their preservation. The area should encourage the production of medicinal plants and the sustainable usage of wild flora, as this will significantly enhance the socioeconomic standing of the local population. medicinal plants and the sustainable usage of wild flora, as this will significantly enhance the socioeconomic standing of the local population.

Fig.2 Different modes of preparation of plants part for the cure of Asthma in District Kachi Bolan.

Fig.3 Plant parts used for Asthma by the people of Mach

Fig.4 Life forms of plants used for Asthma in District Kachi Bolan

percentage

Fig.5 Most species used in the total number of families in research area
Plants and plant derived products reported used for managing Asthma Symptoms

There have been reports of using plants and plant-derived products to treat asthma symptoms. A total of 60 plant species and their traditional uses from 30 different indigenous plants were described in the current study. Local names, family names, life forms, preparation methods, and plant components used for their anti-asthma therapeutic properties were mentioned. A common tree in India, the Middle East, and North Africa is *Boswelliaserrata*. Frankincense, or olibanum, is the common name for the gummy substance or resin that is produced when the bark is peeled off. In Ayurveda, *Boswellia* is commonly used to treat wound healing, asthma, coughs, sores, ulcerative colitis, and arthritis (Donoghue 2008). Chronic asthmatic cough, particularly at night; chest tightness that makes it difficult to breathe deeply; wheezing while exhaling; and occasionally shortness of breath or difficulty breathing when inhaling. When they get a cold or when the temperature changes, some people will experience harsher symptoms.

Medicinal plants for Asthma.

***Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Dalchini)**

Dalchini, or *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Dalchini, or *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Lauraceae), is a fragrant medicinal herb that is utilized in Asia and Western countries as a flowering agent, spice, and preservative in food preparation (Yu et al. 2014; Ranasinghe et al. 2017). It has 250 different species of genes and is grown extensively over the world. According to Kanjilal et al. (1940) and Rao and Gan (2014), *Cinnamomum* are primarily found in tropical and subtropical regions, with 26 species identified in India, primarily in the northeastern region. The therapeutic properties of cinnamon have existed since antiquity. In the past, it was used to assist in treating a number of illnesses, such as digestive and respiratory issues. In more recent times, it has demonstrated potential as an anti-inflammatory and to enhance cognitive performance. And respiratory issues. In more recent times, it has demonstrated potential as an anti-inflammatory and to enhance cognitive performance.

***Papaver somniferum* (Kiokinar)**

(Kiokinar) *Papaver somniferum* One of the most well-known plant species in the Papaveraceae family is *Papaver somniferum*. Ahipena is commonly referred to as bread seed poppy or opium poppy. The seeds of this plant are used to make muffins, breads, and other foods. It is a common source of alkaloids like codeine, morphine (a narcotic analgesic), and several other benzylisoquinoline alkaloids like papaverine (vasodilator), noscapine (a possible anticancer drug and cough suppressant), and sanguinarine (anti-microbial) (Elsevier 2015). The stems and pods are frequently used to arrange flowers.

***Trigonella foenum-graecum* (gon-o-gonjik)**

Go-o-gonjik, or *Trigonella foenum-graecum* One of the plants with these characteristics is *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, also known as fenugreek. It is a self-pollinating annual herbaceous aromatic crop that belongs to the Fabaceae family. Other names for it include bird's foot, Greek hayseed, halba, and methi (Gu et al. 2017). *T. foenum-graecum* leaves and seeds are widely used to create powder and extracts for medicinal use in a variety of studies. Fenugreek has been shown to produce hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, and hypocholesterolemic effects in a number of early animal and human studies. (Mawahib et al 2015) Extract from foenum-graecum (fenugreek) seeds as a supplement for mild asthma. Using the TPM formula, fenugreek syrup was made in a honey solution. When compared to honey and a placebo, the aqueous extract of fenugreek seeds considerably enhanced the quality of life and lung function tests in patients with mild asthma.

***Crocus sativus* (Zaffran).**

Sativus Crocus (Zaffran). Saffron, or *Crocus sativus*, is a tiny perennial plant that is a member of the Iridaceae family. Iran, Afghanistan, Turkey, and Spain are among the many nations that cultivate this plant (Abdullaev, 1993). Carotenoids - crocetin and glycoside crocin, which give saffron its yellow hue, and picrocrocin, an aglycone saffranal that gives it its scent, are known to be present in the stigmas of *C. sativus* (Fernandez and Pandalai 2004). *Crocus sativus* is used as a herbal remedy for a number of illnesses and ailments, such as stomach and cardiovascular issues, amenorrhoea, coughing, and asthma. Saffron's ability to relax smooth muscles may be the basis for some of its medicinal properties

***Thymus vulgaris* (Izbotak).**

Originally from southern Europe, *Thymus vulgaris* is a flowering plant of the Lamiaceae family that is found all over the world (Hosseinzadeh et al., 2015). Since ancient times, people have utilized *Thymus vulgaris* to stimulate saliva, alleviate chest congestion, and soothe sore throats by consuming fresh leaves. The plant is also used to cure worms in children and as an efficient treatment for chest infections (bronchitis, pharyngitis, and whooping cough). Numerous volatile oils found in thyme have strong antibacterial properties and aid in the fight against illness. It is particularly beneficial for coughing, sore throats, and respiratory infections. The oils can help calm a spasmodic cough, relax the respiratory passages, and release phlegm during a respiratory infection.

***Boswellia serrata* (Gound Katerra).**

A moderate to big branching tree, the *Boswellia Serrata* family (Burseraceae) is found in arid mountainous areas of India, Northern Africa, and the Middle East (Maupetit 1984). (Leung et al., 1996) Long-term inflammatory lung conditions have historically been treated with *Boswellia Serrata*. As an anti-asthmatic, *Boswellia* acid seems to be helpful in treating allergic asthma. *Boswellia Serrata* is used to treat osteoarthritis. It is also used for a variety of other conditions, such as diabetes, stroke, and asthma, although there isn't any solid scientific proof for these other uses. Additionally, there is no solid proof that *Boswellia Serrata* is effective against COVID-19.

***Camellia sinensis* (Green tea).**

Camellia sinensis is a member of the Theaceae family, and black, oolong, and green tea

are eaten based on their fermentation process and antioxidant content (Graham 1992, Yamamoto et al. 1997). The most significant health benefits of various polyphenolic compounds contained in green tea, such as flavonols, flavonoids, and phenolic acids, have been intensively explored, and they may account for approximately 20% of dry weight (Dulloo et al., 1999). Green tea is high in antioxidants, which may help reduce asthma-related inflammation. It also contains caffeine, which can temporarily relax your airways.

***Nigella sativa* (Kalonji)**

A medicinal plant that is extensively used worldwide is *Nigella sativa*, which is a member of the Ranunculaceae family. It is widely used in many ancient medical systems, including Siddha, Ayurveda, and Unani and Tibb. Numerous studies have reported the

benefits of *nigella sativa* supplementation for the management of bronchial asthma, including improvements in pulmonary function tests, cytokines, and clinical outcomes (Boskabady et al., 2010; Mahmood et al., 2003; Shazad et al., 2009). According to earlier research, *Nigella sativa* has a positive impact on lung function tests in asthmatic patients, which may indicate that it has bronchodilator properties.

***Trachyspermum ammi* (Ajwain)**

The seeds of ajwain, a member of the Apiaceae family of plants, are widely used as a food additive in India and are mostly employed for their hot, medicinal properties. Copticum is a plant native to Egypt. In many parts of central Europe, Asia, and Iran, particularly the eastern parts of Balochistan, and India (where the majority of crops are grown in the states of Rajasthan, Gujarat, and West Bengal), this plant flourishes in arid and semiarid fields. In 2010 Ahmed et al. cited Zargari (1996). Ajwain helps remove mucus from your nose and relieve coughing, both of which facilitate better breathing. Additionally, it might aid in bronchial tube widening, which would benefit asthmatics. Ajwain seeds are a helpful remedy for respiratory issues. The seeds are well known for keeping the throat and lungs clear of pollutants. People with respiratory issues can breathe easier thanks to ajwain water's ability to relax the airway.

***Curcuma longa* (Haldi)**

Turmeric belongs to the Zingiberaceae (ginger) family and is an evergreen herbaceous plant. It is widely grown throughout Asia, primarily in China and India. Turmeric has been used in India for at least 2500 years and is most likely an Indian invention. The world's tropical and subtropical regions are home to turmeric plants. Although the plant's exact origin is unknown, it is believed to have come from Southeast Asia, most likely India. Everywhere in India, the plant is grown (Kapoor, 2000). After three and six months, we demonstrated that giving children and adolescents with asthma powdered roots in addition to their regular medication, as opposed to a placebo, resulted in fewer nighttime awakenings, decreased use, and improved disease control.

***Osmium sanctum* (Tulsi)**

Osmium sanctum, a member of the Lamiaceae family, is also referred to as holy basil or Tulsi. A common home cure for a variety of conditions, including wounds, pneumonia, liver problems, catarrhal fever, gastrointestinal problems, ophthalmia, hiccoughs, and nostalgia lumbago. Psychosomatic stress disorders, skin conditions, genitourinary problems, and other types of poisoning (Das SK 2006) (Prajapati et al. 2003) Tulsi inhibits the recurrent return of asthmatic symptoms and possesses immunomodulatory properties. Additionally, it possesses anti-allergic and anti-inflammatory properties for the bronchial tubes' mucosal membrane

Table:1 Medicinal plants used for the Treatment of Asthma Disease in Different parts of the Pakistan

S NO	SCIENTIFIC NAME	Local name	Family name	Life from	Part used	Mode of preparation	phytochemical	Toxicity	References
1	<i>Achyranthes</i>	Apamarga	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Decoction powder	Decoction	Saponins	Toxic	Kayani et al., (2014)
2	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Phutkanda	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Leaves	Decoction powder extract	Saponins	Moderate	Kayani et al., (2014)
3	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Skhuwaja	Araceae	Herb	Rhizome	Powder	Asarone	Toxic	Kayani et al., (2014)
4	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Yuza	Alliaceae	Herb	Bulb	Extract	Allicin	Irritation	Rehman et al., (2022)
5	<i>Artemisia</i>	Tarkha	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Infusion	Artemisinin	Low	Dilber et al., (2023)
6	<i>Capparis decidua</i>	Sree Dane	Capparadaceae	Tree	Fruits	infusion	Flavonoids	Non-toxic	Rehman et al., (2022)
7	<i>Capparis decidua</i>	Daila	Capparaceae	Shrub	Branches flowers fruits	Paste Decoction	Alkaloids	Low	Ahmed et al., (2019)
8	<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Ghut khatakai	Asteraceae	Herb	Root	Decoction	Chicoricacid	Low	Rehman et al., (2020)
9	<i>Cousinia stocksii</i>	Narayan band	Asteraceae	perennial	root	Decoction	Flavonoids	Non toxic	Baloch et al., (2013)
10	<i>Cynodon dictylon</i>	Kabal jowar	Poaceae	perennial	Seeds stem	Decoction	Flavonoids	Low	Shah et al., (2020)
11	<i>Datura alba</i>	Datura	Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves and seeds	Infusion	Scopolamine	Toxic	Nisar et al., (2014)
12	<i>Datura innoxia</i>	Toloache	Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves and fruits	Infusion	Alkaloids	Low	Shuaib et al., (2018)

13	<i>Datura metal</i>	Dutra	Solanaceae	leaf	Leaves roots flower	Decoction	Scopolamine	High	Rehman et al., (2022)
14	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	Berbaka	Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Decoction	Alkaloids	Highly toxic	Rehman et al., (2022)
15	<i>Ephedra geradiana</i>	Shomate As mania	Ephederaceae	shrub	stem	Decoction	Ephedrine	Cardiotoxic	Hussian et al., (2011)
16	<i>Ferula assa-foetida</i>	Sup	Apiaceae	Herb	Resin	Powder extract	Ferulic	Hepatotoxic	Kayani et al., (2014)
17	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Pipal	Moraceae	Tree	Leaves bark	Decoction	Flavonoid	Low	Ahmed et al., (2019)
18	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabralinn</i>	Shalako	Fabaceae	Powder direct	Roots	Decoction	Glycyrrhizin	Hypertension	Shedayi and Gulraiz (2014)
19	<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>	KhrasaniAiwain	Solanaceae	Herb		Decoction powder extract	Alkaloids	Poisonous	Kayani et al., (2014)
20	<i>Incarvillea emodi</i>	Kaur	Bignoniaceae	Whole plant	Roots	Decoction	Mussaenoside	Low	Ijaz et al., (2016)
21	<i>Justicia Adhatoda</i>	Bhakkar	Acanthaceae	shrub	Leaves	Powder	Vasicine	Generally safe	Rehman et al., (2023)
22	<i>Lepidium didymium</i>	Salad	Brassicaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Decoction	Glucosinolates	Low	Rehman et al., (2022)
23	<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	PehariPodina	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Powder, Decoction	Menthol	Low	Ahmed et al., (2019)
24	<i>Nigella sativa</i>	Black cumin	Ranunculaceae	Herb	Seeds	Oil extract powder	thymoquinone nigella one	Generally safe	Goreja. (2003)
25	<i>Prosopis Juli flora</i>	KabliKikri	Fabaceae	Shrub	Branches	Paste	Alkaloids	cytotoxic	Ahmed et al., (2019)
26	<i>Salvia nubicola</i>	Khez bee	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Decoction	Flavonoids	Hepatotoxic	Rehman et al., (2022)

27	<i>Senecio chrysanthem</i>	Zergul	Asteraceae	Herb	Flower	Decoction	Pyrrolizidine alkaloids	Hepatotoxic	Rehman et al., (2022)
28	<i>Solanum surattense</i>	Merogony	Solanaceae	Herb	Fruit	Decoction	Solasodine	Toxic	Bahadur et al., (2018)
29	<i>Taxacum officials sapaggr</i>	Dandelion	Asteraceae	Herb	Roots leaves and flower	Infusion	Taraxasterol	Low	Ahmed et al., (2020)
30	<i>Withania Somnfera</i>	Winter cherry	Solanaceae	shrub	Leaves roots flower bark and stem	Powder extract roots and leaves for medicinal use	Alkaloids saponins and steroids	Generally safe	Parvaiz et al., (2018)

Table: 2 Medicinal plants used for the Treatment of Asthma Disease in District Kachi Bolan Tehsil Mach

S. No	Scientific <u>Name</u>	Local Name	Family	Life Form	Part used	Mode of preparation	FC	RFC	UR	UV
1	<i>Adhatoda vasica L.</i>	Barg-e-Aroosa	Acanthaceae	Perennial shrub	Leaves and sometime roots	Leaves are commonly brewed into teas or prepared as extract	2	0.01	2	1
2	<i>Allium sativum L.</i>	Lasan	Amaryllidaceae	Perennial	Bulb	Fresh or dried bulb used in cooking teas	2	0.01	6	0.3
3	<i>Allium sativum L.</i>	Tom	Amaryllidaceae	Herb	Bulb	Raw/tea/soup	2	0.01	4	0.5
4	<i>Althea officinalis L.</i>	Marsh mallow	Myrtaceae	Perennial	Roots leaves flower	Infusion	2	0.01	2	1
5	<i>Astragalus L.</i>	Hung	Fabaceae	Perennial	Roots	Decoction	2	0.01	2	0.5
6	<i>Black cardamom L.</i>	Badi elaichi	Zingiberaceae	Spice	Seeds leaves	Toasting	6	0.05	8	0.75
7	<i>Black pepper L.</i>	Kali march	Piperaceae	Spice	Seed	Grinding	6	0.05	8	0.75
8	<i>Boswellia serrata W.</i>	Gund Katterra	Burseraceae	Annually	Resin	Extract of the resin	4	0.03	3	1.3
9	<i>Camellia sinensis L.</i>	Green tea	Theaceae	Shrub	Leaves	dried and steeped in hot water	8	0.06	10	0.8
10	<i>Cinnamon L.</i>	Dalchini	Lauraceae	Spice	Bark of shoots	Grinding	2	0.01	4	0.5
11	<i>Cordia myxa L.</i>	Lasura	Boraginaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Boil lasora fruit or leaves in water to make decoction	2	0.01	4	0.5
12	<i>Crocus sativus L.</i>	Zaffran	Lridaceae	Herb	Stigma	Decoction	4	0.03	8	0.5
13	<i>Curcuma longa L.</i>	Haldi	Zingiberaceae	Herbaceous	Rhizome	Powdered rhizome used in teas decoction or as a spice	4	0.03	5	0.8
14	<i>Ephedra sinica L.</i>	Ma Huang	Ephederaceae	Shrub	Stem	Capsules	2	0.01	3	0.6

15	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra L.</i>	Multi	Fabaceae	Perennial	Roots	Decoction or infusion of roots	2	0.01	3	0.6
16	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra L.</i>	Licorice	Fabaceae	Perennial	Roots	Decoction	2	0.01	2	1
17	<i>Hordeum vulgare L.</i>	Joy	Poaceae	It is an annual grass	Barley water	Barley is consumed in various forms including as whole grains flour and in beverages	2	0.01	2	1
18	<i>Jaggery S.</i>	Gur			Swartness	Natural sweetener from sugarcane juice or date palm sap	8	0.06	9	0.8
19	<i>Juglans regia L.</i>	Akhrot	Juglandaceae	Tree	Leaves	Oil/paste/tea	2	0.01	4	0.5
20	<i>Nigella sativa L.</i>	Kalonji	Ranunculaceae	Herbaceous annual plant	Seed	Seed oil powdered seeds taken orally	2	0.01	9	0.2
21	<i>Num harmala L.</i>	Kisankoor	Zygophyllaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Smoke	4	0.03	5	0.8
22	<i>Oligomeris linifolia machbrick (vahl) M.</i>	Shootk	Resedaceae	Herb	Seed	Decoction powder	4	0.03	2	0.5
23	<i>Osmium sanctum L.</i>	Tulsi	Lamiaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Infusion or decoction of leaves	2	0.01	2	1
24	<i>Papaver somniferum L.</i>	Kokinar	Clusiaceae	Herb	Seed	Decoction paste	10	0.08	9	1.1
25	<i>Thymus serpyllum L.</i>	Izbotak	Lamiaceae	Perennial	Aerial part of flower	Decoction/tea	2	0.01	6	0.3
26	<i>Trachyspermum ammi L.</i>	Ajwain	Apiaceae	Herbaceous	Seeds	Seeds crushed or ground	4	0.03	4	1
27	<i>Trigonella frenum-graecum L.</i>	Gon o gonjik	Fabaceae	Herb	Leaves/roots	Paste infusion	6	0.05	8	0.75

28	<i>Verbascum Thapsus L.</i>	Mullein	Scrophulariaceae	Biennial	Leaves	Infusion	2	0.01	3	0.6
29	<i>White cumin L.</i>	Safaid zeera	Apiaceae	Spice	Seeds	Rosting	4	0.03	3	1.3
30	<i>Zingiber officinale W.</i>	Adrak	Zingiberaceae	Perennial	Rhizome	Fresh or dried rhizome used in teas decoction or powders	4	0.03	7	0.57

Conclusion

The most prevalent chronic illness in children, asthma is a serious non-communicable disease (NCD) that can affect both adults and children. Asthma symptoms, which include coughing, wheezing, shortness of breath, and tightness in the chest, are brought on by inflammation and constriction of the lungs' tiny airways. Bolan-Tehsil Mach was the first study to highlight the therapeutic potential of common species found in the territory. Balochistan boasts nine main natural zones with distinctive biodiversity. Owing to its distinct environment, the nation has a vast array of indigenous and medicinal plants spread over its vast territory. In Pakistan, there are 1572 general and 5521 species of flowering plants, 400–600 of which are significant for medicine. There are currently few scientific studies on medicinal plants; thus, further research is required to fully understand how phytotherapy might be used to treat asthma. Even though medicinal plants undeniably have the potential to fight disease, but there is still a problem that needs to be discussed and should be researched regarding the proper use of ethnobotanical plants is the amount or dose used in herbal medication in the process of preparation.

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